

A Novel Method for Spot Test Detection of Alcohols

B. R. SAHU

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University,
Raipur-492 010

and

U. TANDON*

Department of Chemistry, Govt. Science College, Raipur

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ALCOHOLS are important not only industrially but also in energy and environmental problems. Some methods are reported for their detection¹⁻⁷ and determination in trace quantity. A new method for detection of alcohols, using vanadium(V)-N-phenylbenzohydroxamate is described here. The method is simple, rapid and fairly sensitive.

The violet complex of vanadium(V)-N-phenylbenzohydroxamate⁸ in chloroform solution is strikingly susceptible to traces of alcohols. Microquantities of alcohols change the colour of the complex from violet to finally pale yellow. With this observation, the proposed method was developed and successfully employed to several mono and polyhydric alcohols and also in the analysis of some pharmaceutical and industrial samples. Identical results are obtained when violet red complex of V(V)-N-benzylbenzohydroxamate is used.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Chloroform used was alcohol free. A 0.1% (w/v) chloroformic solution of N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was used. Ammonium metavanadate solution was so prepared that 1.0 ml of it contained 40-44 μg of V(V).

Preparation of the reagent solution : In a separatory funnel 2.0 ml of vanadium(V) solution was diluted to 10-15 ml with distilled water and acidity of this was adjusted at 3-8 M HCl. After adding hydroxamic acid solution (10 ml), the contents were thoroughly shaken for 1 min and the violet coloured organic extract was separated completely and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Volume of the extract was made upto 25 ml with chloroform and the absorbance was found to be 0.225 at 530 nm. The reagent solution may also be prepared directly from the solid complex⁹.

Procedure for the identification of alcohols : 1.0 ml of the reagent solution taken in a semi-micro test tube was mixed with the alcohol (about 0.1 ml or 0.1 g) under examination and shaken gently for 1 min. In case colour change was not visible, the solution was warmed with intermittent shaking in a water bath at 50-55° and examined after cooling to room temperature.

Preliminary experiments showed that the use of violet extract of absorbance ranging from 0.15 to 0.30 leads to correct colour change observation.

Above and below this range, the change in colour is not easily detectable. Results of identification of alcohols are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COLOUR CHANGE OF VANADIUM(V)-N-PHENYLBENZOHYDROXAMATE

Alcohol	Change in violet extract	
	Time	Colour
Methanol	Immediate	Almost colourless
Ethanol	Immediate	Faint yellow
2-Methoxy ethanol ⁺	Immediate	Pink
	3-5 Min ⁺	Almost colourless
<i>n</i> -Propanol	Immediate	Pale yellow
2-Ethoxy ethanol ⁺	5 Min	Pink
	2 Min ⁺	Pale yellow
<i>n</i> -Butanol	Rapid	Faint yellow
<i>Isobutanol</i> ⁺	5 Min	Pale yellow
Amyl alcohol	Rapid	Pink
	2 Min ⁺	Faint yellow
<i>Isoamyl alcohol</i> ⁺	3-4 Min	Yellow
2-Butoxy ethanol ⁺	3-4 Min	Yellow
Diacetone alcohol ⁺	30-30 Min	Light pink
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 Min	Pale yellow
Cyclohexanol ⁺	3-5 Min	Almost colourless
Benzyl alcohol ⁺	3-5 Min	Yellow
<i>n</i> -Decanol	5-10 Min	Pale yellow
Glycol	Immediate	Faint yellow
Glycerol ⁺	Gradual	Pink
Menthol ⁺	Very slow	Light pink

*Violet colour of the extract fades in cold.

Colour change is observed only on warming.

Determination of limits of identification : Solutions of alcohols (in water or benzene) under test were suitably diluted and limits of identification determined. One drop of the diluted test solution was treated with four drops of the reagent solution as described above. Table 2 shows the results.

TABLE 2—LIMITS OF ALCOHOLS IDENTIFIED BY THE PRESENT METHOD*

Alcohol	Quantity (mg)	Alcohol	Quantity (mg)
Methanol	2.0	Amyl alcohol	3.5
Ethanol	2.5	<i>Iso</i> -amyl alcohol	5.0
2-Methoxy ethanol	3.0	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	10.3
2-Ethoxy ethanol	4.5	<i>n</i> -Decanol	10.4
<i>n</i> -Propanol	2.5	Glycol	44.0
2-Butoxy ethanol	6.0	Diacetone alcohol	23.5
<i>n</i> -Butanol	3.0	Benzyl alcohol	5.0
<i>Iso</i> -butanol	3.5	Cyclohexanol	14.5

*The limits of identification of alcohols were found to be the same with vanadium(V)-N-benzylbenzohydroxamate.

Interference : When using the test, it should be remembered that the colour change is brought about also by some other classes of compounds. Phenols and cresols respond to the test to give orange red, lemon yellow, light blue, yellow green, golden yellow or dark green colour. It has been observed that any of these colours is not developed in the reagent solution by alcohols where the colour change finally results to faint yellow or pale yellow. With this difference in colour, alcohols can be very easily distinguished from phenols and cresols.

Dioxane, methyl-*isobutyl* ketone and acetone interfere whereas the common water-immiscible

organic solvents like benzene, toluene, xylene, diethyl ether, petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and halogenated hydrocarbons such as carbon tetrachloride, *o*-dichlorobenzene, chlorobenzene and dilute alkali do not interfere.

Applications of the method :

1. *Detection of hydroxy carboxylic acids :* Hydroxy acids which show the properties of alcohols as well as of acids also cause the colour change. With the help of this test the acids which contain -OH group can be differentiated from those having no hydroxyl group. This further extends the usefulness of the test.

2. *Detection in pharmaceutical and industrial samples :* The efficacy of the method was seen by employing it to the detection of alcohol in some pharmaceuticals viz., tenoferon drops, paracetamol, vanvitone, streptomycin base, chloramphenicol and industrial samples like wine, beer and rum. All these samples were found to respond to the test of alcohol.

The results given in Tables 1 and 2 show that the present method is satisfactory with respect to reliability and sensitivity. The method is quick and the preparative operations are simple.

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